

Understanding Workers Adoption of Productivity Mobile Applications: A Fuzzy Set Qualitative Comparative Analysis (fsQCA)

Introduction

Mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets are increasingly more present in our lives. According to a recent market analysis 78% of the world's population owns a smartphone, more than 50% have tablets and about 10% already own a smartwatch device (Deloitte, 2017). Noticeably, more than 80% of these devices use the Android operating system (OS), which has become the most popular operative system (OS) for mobile devices (ONTSI, 2016).

For these devices, a wealth of application software (apps) provide answers to users' needs. One of most popular apps category is that of productivity apps, that is to say, applications dedicated to creating and modifying information such as documents, presentations, worksheets, databases, charts, graphs, etc. (Davis, 2017). This type of application, which increases the productivity of office workers and transforms the way we work, is becoming essential in today's knowledge economy (Burning Glass Technologies, 2015).

Given the relevance of productivity apps, it is important for businesses as well as mobile technology developers to have a firm understanding of the personal characteristics of workers that use productivity apps, since this may influence their productivity at the workplace. It is also important from a theoretical perspective to examine whether productivity apps can be related to users' personal characteristics as well as other type of information such as sociodemographic and Internet-usage information. Therefore, this study aims to analyze how combinations of personality

factors, sociodemographic variables and Internet use influence the adoption of productivity mobile apps by workers.

Previous work showed the relevance of personality in relation to technology adoption (Vishwanath, 2005), including adoption of social media (Ross et al., 2009), location-based services (Chorley et al., 2015), or mobile apps (Xu et al., 2016), among others. However, the scientific literature is scarce in studies about adoption that combine personality, sociodemographic and Internet use factors.

This paper contributes to the literature on technology adoption by uncovering the relevance of the extraversion and agreeableness factors for the adoption of productivity apps. Our study also provides relevant insight for software developers to target specific segments interested in the use of productivity software in their mobile devices.

The present work is organized as follows: first, the different characteristics of the personality and the sociodemographic variables that will be used as antecedents of adoption of mobile productivity applications are defined, with a review of the influence of these factors on adoption of information systems. The methodology section explains the double strategy used for the collection of data through questionnaire and the collection of applications directly from Android phones. After a brief explanation of the analysis technique used, fsQCA, we present the conclusions contributions and limitations of the work as well as suggestions for future research.

Personality, socio-demographic variables and Internet usage as Antecedents to the Adoption and Use of Technology

Research on technology adoption began in the late 1970s with work that focused broadly on users' views of technology and their satisfaction. The theories in this stream incorporate some of the central concepts from social and behavior sciences in order to

predict and understand users' adoption of technology, notably is the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), the general theory underlying multiple information-systems specific theories such as the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1989) and the Unified Theory for Acceptance and Use of Technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003).

With the adoption of the Internet in a massive way since early 1990's, some researchers began to study the influence of sociodemographic and personality variables, arriving at the conclusion that research on the use of Internet needs more variance than the traditional adoption models (McElroy et al., 2007). Therefore, following the call of McElroy et al. (2007), this study analyzes the impact of personality, demographic and Internet use variables on the adoption of productivity applications by workers.

Personality Factors

A vast amount of research work has focused on the relationship between personality factors and technology. Previous work has concentrated on technology adoption (Vishwanath, 2005, Ross et al., 2009), Internet use (Landers & Lounsbury, 2006), problems in the use of mobile devices (Bianchi & Phillips, 2005), and the adoption of specific type of applications (Chorley et al., 2015). This section reviews the different characteristics that influence personality factors, the relationship between personality factors and the adoption of new technologies, and the propensity to adopt productivity applications. Our aim is to determine the current state of the art on the adoption of productivity applications according to the personality of individuals.

The Big Five Inventory scale (BFI-10) has been used extensively in the scientific literature to measure five personality factors: extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience (Rammstedt & John, 2007).

The extraversion factor implies an energetic focus both in the social and in the material world, including features such as being a social, active, assertive and emotionally positive person (John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008). Focusing on the impact of personality aspects on mobile phone adoption and usage, it should be noted how extroverted people are most likely to possess a smartphone. Extroverts do not replace offline relationships with online ones, although they are prone to using Internet to maintain them, and are inclined to share information with others (Amiel & Sargent, 2004), key characteristics associated with the use of social networking applications (Xu et al., 2016). On the contrary, extraversion is negatively associated with the use of computer games (Chittaranjan et al., 2013) and mobile games applications (Xu et al., 2016). In relation to education, extraversion is associated with the professional study of economics, law, political science and medicine (Vedel, 2016). As for extraversion and its relation to productivity apps, it is worth referring the study by Lane & Manner (2012) who also tried to understand the personality characteristics associated with the use of smartphone applications. ~~Among their results are that~~ Extroverted individuals showed greater importance to gaming applications, recognizing less importance to those corresponding to productivity (Lane & Manner, 2012). By contrast, Chittaranjan et al. (2013) point to a positive relationship between this personality factor and the use of Office applications and calendars. Thus, the studies relating extraversion and productivity apps show contradictory results.

On the other hand, the agreeableness factor presents a community vision, showing characteristics such as altruism, confidence and modesty (John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008). Different studies agree that the tolerance and permissiveness that characterizes agreeable people makes them more likely to accept new technologies easily and spend more time on the Internet (Devaraj et al., 2008). The agreeableness factor is not a

significant predictor of good work performance (Barrick & Mount, 1991) and shows little relationship to law, business and economic studies (Vedel, 2016). Lastly, although agreeable people use extensively the phone to make calls (Lane & Manner, 2012), the agreeableness factor has been found to be negatively correlated with the use of Office and Calendar applications, as well as video / audio / music, mail and SMS services in Internet (Chittaranjan et al., 2013).

The factor of conscientiousness is characterized by the control of the impulses, facilitating the accomplishment of tasks and the achievement of objectives. Conscious people think before acting, follow norm and rules, as well as planning, organizing and prioritizing tasks (John et al., 2008). The practicality that characterizes conscious people would make them less interested in entertainment applications, such as music and video (Chittaranjan et al., 2013) or social networks (Ryan & Xenos, 2011; Hughes et al., 2012). By contrast, it would be expected that people with these characteristics would be attracted by the use of productivity apps, however, there are no conclusive results that support such beliefs (Xu et al., 2016). The conscientiousness factor is important for the development of all kind of jobs (Barrick & Mount, 1991), although it shows a low relation with branches of study such as arts and humanities (Vedel, 2016).

People with characteristics of neuroticism counterpoise emotional stability with negative emotionality, expressed by anxious feelings, nervousness, sadness and tension (John et al., 2008). The lack of confidence, characteristic of these people, prompts them to consider new technologies and services as threatening and stressful, resulting in less Internet use (Devaraj et al., 2008; Tuten & Bosnjak, 2001). In addition, this factor is negatively related to the perception of utility and behavior control, which reduces the intention to incorporate new technologies in daily life (Uffen et al., 2013). However, there are also studies that support that this personality factor pushes individuals to turn

to new technologies to face their problems, either by looking to increase sociability via social networks (Ryan & Xenos, 2011), or by modulating their bad feelings through online shopping (Tuten, & Bosnjak, 2001). In relation to studies, these individuals tend to study arts, humanities and psychology (Vedel, 2016). As for the preferences of applications of neurotic people, the literature is not conclusive. According to Lane & Manner (2012), neurotics give greater importance to travel applications, while productivity and utility applications are the least important to them. However, Chittaranjan et al. (2013) indicate that emotional stability is negatively correlated with the use of Office and Calendar applications. These results show that both emotional stability and, its opposite, neurotic personality would have a negative relation with the adoption of useful applications.

Finally, openness corresponds to an original, deep person with a curious mind (John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008). People with this characteristic are more likely to adopt new technologies (Constantiou et al., 2006; Tuten & Bosnjak, 2001). In the work environment, openness to experience is shown as a predictor of learning (Barrick & Mount, 1991), and stands out for its relation to humanities, arts, psychology and political science (Vedel, 2016). In relation to the adoption of productivity apps, according to Chittaranjan et al. (2013), this factor is negatively correlated with Office, Calendar and SMS applications.

Socio-demographic variables and Internet usage

Along with the personality characteristics of users of Android applications, this study focuses on sociodemographic variables. The analysis includes the variables of gender, age, and level of studies for workers who are Android users. In addition, in order to contextualize the degree of relationship of the users with the new technologies, the analysis also includes the variable of Internet usage.

Sociodemographic variables have been taken into account to study the adoption of technologies. Some studies have focused on the technology impact on users, according to their profile (Pedersen & Ling, 2003), while others have focused on relating users' characteristics with the operation of the mobile terminals and their satisfaction with them (Balakrishnan, & Yeow, 2007).

In relation to age, Walsh et al. (2010) point out that young users were more likely to adopt mobile devices, while Plaza et al. (2011) point out that older people use phones to communicate with their relatives, as aids to memory and daily life, enjoyment, self-realization, and as tools to feel safe.

According to the gender variable, Castells et al. (2004) indicate that female users give to their mobile terminal greater value as a fashionable object and as a key channel for maintaining personal relationships; on the contrary, male users give value to their mobile terminal as an instrument of achieve their goals.

In the adoption of mobile phones, the experience and aptitude of individuals towards new technologies have shown to be relevant, since users more technologically advanced and technologically oriented can influence the perception of ease of use (Van Biljon & Kotzé, 2007). As a result, the use of the Internet, understood as the amount of online services used, can reflect the capacity and technological orientation of individuals, as well as their capacity to deal with new technologies such as productivity apps.

Concerning the adoption of specific applications, Chittaranjan et al. (2013) indicate that men were more likely to use Office applications, in addition to games and Youtube.

Veríssimo (2016) shows through the fsQCA analysis that age can explain the non-use of mobile banking applications. Thus, the characteristic of less than 35 years is present in different models explaining the non-use of the app (Veríssimo, 2016).

From the literature review and analysis, the following proposition emerged: the

adoption or not adoption of productivity apps can be explained as a combination of personality factors and sociodemographic variables. According to the previous antecedents, Figure 1 presents the study's model.

Figure 1 here.

Methods

Data Collection and Measures

This study collected data directly from users' mobile phones, and form an online questionnaire. Participants installed in their phone an application called Pinkerton, following a process similar to the one used in other works (Seneviratne et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2016). For each mobile phone, the following data is collected: OS version, status of the option about download from unknown sources, if it is in developer mode, or if it has been rooted. For each application in the phone, the following data is collected: name of the application, package, version, source from which it was downloaded, category of the application following Google Play or Amazon classification, and if the application includes a launcher.

The direct collection of data from the individual's personal phone through a mobile app solves problems of bias derived from the use of self-complemented surveys. Previous work has shown significant differences between the self-responses of research participants and their actual behavior, especially in the number and duration of mobile calls (Abeele et al., 2013). Other studies have also shown that due to the large number of applications that the user may have installed, the user may find it difficult to enumerate all the installed applications and its daily use (Xu et al. Al., 2016), avoiding the possibility of introducing biases of answers by social desirability.

Sociodemographic variables (studies, age and sex), frequency of internet use and personality (extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism and openness to experience) were collected throughout an online questionnaire. To study users' personality, we draw on the Big Five Inventory personality model in its 10-item version (BFI-10), which summarizes the information of 44 items (BFI-44). The use of this instrument allowed us to include variables related to the personality, without losing excessive information.

For the study, 701 mobile devices were analyzed, of which 699 devices presented useful information for this study. The scanning of these devices collected a total of 27,740 applications, after obviating those corresponding to the device OS. Thus, on average, users had 39.69 applications installed on their devices. Of the 701 devices, we have selected the 497 that are owned by working users. Table 1 shows the sociodemographic characteristics of the 699 users sample.

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From the 497 working users the characteristics with greater representation are: men (57.95%), over 34 years-old (71.03%), and with studies in higher-education (university level) (60.76%). Regarding the adoption of productivity applications, it can be seen that 19.92% of users do not use any of such applications, while about half (48.09%) have one and two applications in their device, corresponding the remaining 31.99% to those with the greater adoption of this type of applications.

Research Methodology

In order to validate the proposition posed previously, we apply a fsQCA analysis, since its focus on “causal recipes” (Ragin, 2008) makes it uniquely suited to analyze complex complementarities among factors (Ganter & Hacker, 2014; Henik, 2015; Woodside,

2013; Cova & Rodríguez-Monroy, 2016; Ryan, 2017), as it is the case in our research.

This analysis has been carried out in three phases (Ragin, 2008; Schneider &

Wagemann, 2012). First, we perform a calibration of the conditions and outputs.

Second, an analysis of necessary conditions was completed with the objective of determining if the independent variables are necessary conditions to produce the output.

Thirdly, an analysis of sufficiency conditions has been carried out in order to determine the conditions or combinations of these that are sufficient to cause the output. To carry out this analysis the fsQCA 2.5 software has been used (Ragin, 2008).

In the calibration, the dichotomous variables (labor activity, age and sex) take either 0 or 1, with the first value corresponding to non-inclusion and the second being included.

Continuous variables were calibrated by taking the percentile less than 5 as 0, and therefore, not belonging, the 50th percentile with 0.5, referred to the maximum level of uncertainty; and the 95th percentile as 1, corresponding to the most belonging. In the case of adoption of productivity apps, the absence of application took the value 0, between 1 and 2 app was given the value of maximum uncertainty, 0.5, with 1 being the case with those with more than two applications. The personality variables have been calibrated as 1 non-membership value (giving value 0); maximum uncertainty at 3 (value 0.5), mean value of the scale; and belonging to 5 (value 1).

Following Ragin (2000), cut-off points with values of 0.80 of consistency have been used to explain the adoption of applications. However, in the case of non-adoption, lower cutoff points have been used due to the lack of cases reaching those values, with the intention of obtaining results that could be orientative, although not conclusive. It is also important to note the importance of consistency and coverage values in the fsQCA analysis. These parameters are between 0 and 1, the first responding to the proportion in which the model covers the studied solution, and the second, to the proportion presented

by the proposed model among the cases containing the studied solution. The consistency value is similar to the correlation coefficient, constituting a test of solution adequacy, while the coverage value resembles the coefficient of determination (R^2) (Woodside, 2013). Thus, we will consider a solution when the consistency value is above 0.65 (Ragin, 2000), although values above 0.75 are recommended; in addition, the coverage should be between 0.25 and 0.65, although it can be accepted when the values distant from these slightly (Urueña & Hidalgo, 2016).

Main Findings

Table 2 shows that studies and responsibility variables are close to constitute a necessary condition for the adoption or not of productivity apps, showing a value close to 1 (Legewie, 2013). Other variables would show a sufficiency relation, in which these would constitute a subset of the condition presence of productivity apps. This means that this presence will occur if the variable showing a sufficient relation is present, but other conditions can also produce this fact (Legewie, 2013). Therefore, this first analysis corroborates the need for further study how the combination of these variables influences the presence of productivity apps.

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As for the results of the analysis of sufficiency conditions, regarding the adoption of applications according to personality factors, the model differentiates three subsets (paths 1a, 1b, 1c in table 3). It is worth noticing the positive values of the extraversion and agreeableness factors.

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According to the first subset, the output of the adoption of productivity apps is determined by the presence in individuals of the characteristics of agreeableness,

whereas it would present negative values of responsibility, neuroticism and openness to experience. The second subset establishes how the characteristics that must be present are extraversion, agreeableness, not responsibility and not neuroticism. The third model includes the factors of extraversion, agreeableness, responsibility, neuroticism and openness to experience.

The results of the analysis of non-adoption of productivity apps according to the personality factors do not provide values of consistency that reach the recommended acceptance criteria of consistency, between 75% and 80%, having not been possible the determination of a cut-off point greater than 0.75. Therefore, this kind of results need to be treated carefully. This solution contemplates two subsets (paths 2a, 2b) of factors to explain that there is no adoption, highlighting the absence of agreeableness and neuroticism and the presence of responsibility.

As for the sociodemographic characteristics of the individuals who adopt the applications, two subsets are obtained (paths 1a and 1b in table 4); in both subsets, it is worth noticing the presence of higher-education studies and males. The first subset is characterized by being men, with studies and low use of Internet services. Likewise, young men with studies define the second subset.

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In reference to the explanation of the non-adoption and sociodemographic variables, we have also obtained low-level consistency and coverage values. However, the results of the model are shown for guidance. Thus, it should be noted the presence of women and age above 35 years. On the other hand, the first subset, in addition to the two common characteristics, presents higher-education studies and a low use of online services, while

the second one is characterized by no higher level in studies and high use of online services.

To strengthen our understanding on adoption of productivity apps, we also analyzed the age variable and the personality factors (Table 5). The choice of age is determined by not being present in all subsets of the explanatory model of adoption, in addition to showing both positive and negative values. In addition, it is considered a variable of great importance when it comes to understanding technological adoption (Morris & Venkatesh, 2000).

<< TABLE 5 HERE >>

From the analysis of the variables age and personality together, we obtained a model formed of six subsets (paths 1a-1f) that explain the adoption of the productivity apps. Of the result, it is worth mentioning the positive presence of the factors of agreeableness and extraversion, as opposed to the negative values of neuroticism and age.

The most relevant differences are found when addressing the responsibility factor. This personality factor presents high values only when the users of the devices are under 35 years old, being able to present also high values of openness to the experience. On the contrary, when they are not responsible, age may not be present in the solution. Thus, if the values of responsibility are low, age seems to play a less relevant role (Figure 1).

Discussion

Our literature review has shown the influence of both personality factors and sociodemographic variables on the adoption of new technologies and mobile applications. This study delves into the different combinations of personality factors and sociodemographic characteristics that create the conditions for the adoption - or not adoption - of productivity apps by workers.

We highlight the positive value of the factors of extraversion and agreeableness for the adoption of productivity apps. Thus, the relevance of the extroverted character factor in the subsets that explain the adoption of productivity apps contradicts the studies that indicated that extroverted people give less importance to these kind of applications (Lane & Manner, 2012). Likewise, the relevance in the analysis of the agreeableness factor contrasts with the studies that indicated a negative correlation of this factor with the use of productive apps such as Office and Calendar (Chittaranjan et al., 2013). Our results are aligned with studies showing the capability of agreeable people to adopt new technologies (Devaraj et al., 2008), their willingness to the work environment, and their relationship with studies such as law, business and economics, areas for which productivity apps can be very useful.

In addition, these factors with positive values have a limited presence in the subsets that explain the non-adoption of productivity apps, being in these cases combined with positive values of responsibility, factors that seem very relevant when explaining non-adoption, especially when combined with an age over 35 years old.

Therefore, the responsibility factor is critical in the non-adoption of productivity apps. It appears positive in all subsets explaining non-adoption and negative in three of the subsets that explain adoption. This factor could be key in the case of users over 35 years old, giving the combination of responsible and age over 35 as a result of non-adoption (although the model did not achieve the established consistency level for acceptance, for five tenths). However, the presence of high values of responsibility would result in adoption in the event that users were under 35years.

As a hypothesis, we can state that people with high scores in responsibility are not mobile workers, since they are more efficient while in their work place and within working hours, and use their mobile device to perform other productive activities. Thus,

relating this hypothesis to the results of responsible people in their working life, Judge et al. (1999) point out that the responsibility factor positively predicted success in a professional career. Additionally, responsible people are positively related to a beneficial interaction between work and non-work roles (Michel, et al., 2011) and negatively correlated with the interference of family life in the workplace (Kinnunen, et al., 2003), i.e. they separate private life and work. Therefore, use of productivity apps in mobile devices may have less relevance to the working life of responsible people.

In relation to the subsets that explain adoption and present positive values of responsibility, it should be noted that for users under 35 years old, the presence of productivity apps may be due to the level of technology savviness of these users, and to the high degree of integration of the new technologies in their life. These people also present high values of openness to the experience, and will be inclined to try different kinds of applications.

On the other hand, neuroticism shows a negative relation with the adoption of productivity apps. These results are in agreement with previous work (Ryan & Xenos, 2011), besides granting less importance to productivity apps compared to other type of applications such as travel.

Finally, in relation to gender and study level, it is worth noticing the presence of the male and studies variables in the different subsets that explain the adoption of productivity apps.

Conclusions

The mobile revolution has changed our daily experiences, including the way we work. Productivity apps are a key element in such revolution. This study contributes to the research on the adoption of productivity apps by identifying the personality traits on

individual users and correlating them to the adoption or non-adoption of productivity apps. We have focused on users of Android applications.

Our analysis combines personality factors, sociodemographic variables and Internet usage to study the adoption of productivity apps. The extraversion and agreeableness factors emerged as central to the adoption of productivity apps, while the responsibility factor would constraint the adoption among those over 35 years, but not precluding adoption among those under 35 years. This work reinforces theories that point out the importance of personality in adopting mobile apps. In the same way, it serves to contrast previous research that provided contradictory results on the characteristics that affect the object of study.

The approach to study the adoption of productivity applications through the combination of the different variables, and the applications of fsQCA analysis proves to be correct and constitutes an interesting alternative to the traditional statistical analysis.

Our study has managerial implications for business in general, and application developers in particular. First, previous studies have identified how productivity apps can drive efficiency and effectiveness in different areas of the enterprise (Väättäjä, 2012). If companies want to encourage their adoption, they need to pay special attention to those having a responsibility personality and over 35 years old; such a group may require specific awareness programs and training about the advantages and use of productivity apps. Second, research on interface designs revealed that some design features are more or less effective depending on personality characteristics; for instance, badges work better on introverts while progress bar is preferred by people with high level of agreeableness (Codish & Ravid, 2014). Developers of productivity apps may need to include features to maintain engagement with the app by extroverted and agreeable people, possibly including gamification techniques (Kumar, 2013); by

contrast, responsible people are less likely to be motivated by socially-based technologies and different techniques may need to be applied.

Future research can take this study further by addressing several limitations. First, our sample was drawn from Android users, leaving out those who have other OS such as iOS or Windows Phone. Future investigations will need to extend the study to users of other OS, and to analyze potential differences between the different user groups.

Likewise, it would be interesting to extend the study to apps outside the productivity category, and to extend it to other domains such as tourism or transportation. Finally, this research analyzes the information collected from scanning of the mobile terminals at a given time; hence, it is not possible to analyze issues such as the evolution in the use of applications, which is another potential line of future research.

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Figure 1. Research model

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

Variable	Response category	N	%
Gender	Female (0)	340	48,64%
	Male (1)	359	51,36%
	Total	699	100%
Age	≤ 34 years old (0)	235	33,62%
	> 34 years old (1)	464	66,38%
	Total	699	100%
Level of Studies	Primary level (0)	5	0,72%
	Secondary level (0,5)	300	42,92%
	Higher-Education level (1)	394	56,37%
Productivity Apps	0 app (0)	145	20,74%
	Between 1 and 2 apps (0,5)	333	47,64%
	>2 apps (1)	221	31,62%
	Total	699	100%

Note: the value of the response categories in parentheses corresponds to the value they take for the fsQCA analysis

Table 2. Necessary conditions

Condition	Productivity Apps			
	Adoption		Non Adoption	
	Consistency	Coverage	Consistency	Coverage
Age	0.70	0.55	0.72	0.45
~ Age	0.30	0.58	0.28	0.42
Studies	0.88	0.64	0.90	0.51
~ Studies	0.33	0.81	0.36	0.70
Gender	0.62	0.60	0.52	0.40
~ Gender	0.38	0.50	0.48	0.50
Internet usage	0.74	0.69	0.76	0.56
~ Internet usage	0.52	0.74	0.57	0.63
Extraversion	0.68	0.68	0.70	0.56
~ Extraversion	0.56	0.71	0.60	0.59
Agreeableness	0.75	0.68	0.77	0.55
~ Agreeableness	0.51	0.74	0.56	0.64
Responsibility	0.83	0.62	0.88	0.51
~ Responsibility	0.35	0.78	0.36	0.63
Neuroticism	0.53	0.73	0.55	0.60
~ Neuroticism	0.71	0.67	0.75	0.56
Openness to Experience	0.78	0.66	0.81	0.54
~ Openness to Experience	0.45	0.75	0.49	0.64
Age	0.70	0.55	0.72	0.45
~ Age	0.30	0.58	0.28	0.42

Values below 0.65 do not meet the criteria for necessary conditions

Table 3. Results of the complex solution (personality factors)

	Adoption*			Non Adoption**	
	1a	1b	1c	2a	2b
Extraversion		●	●	●	
Agreeableness	●	●	●	○	○
Responsibility	○	○	●	●	●
Neuroticism	○	○	●	○	○
Openness to Experience	○		●		●
Consistency	0.81	0.81	0.80	0.70	0.69
Raw coverage	0.24	0.27	0.38	0.43	0.46
Unique coverage	0.02	0.02	0.16	0.02	0.05
Solution coverage	0.45			0.47	
Solution consistency	0.81			0.69	

Black circles represent the presence of a condition while voids circles indicate negation.

Table 4. Results of the complex solution (sociodemographic variables and Internet usage)

	Adoption*		Non Adoption**	
	1a	1b	2a	2b
Age		○	●	●
Studies	●	●	●	○
Gender	●	●	○	○
Internet usage	○		○	●
Consistency	0.83	0.71	0.74	0.75
Raw coverage	0.33	0.13	0.18	0.09
Unique coverage	0.25	0.05	0.11	0.02
Solution coverage	0.38		0.20	
Solution consistency	0.78		0.74	

Black circles represent the presence of a condition while voids circles indicate negation.

Table 5. Results of the complex solution (personality and age)

	Adoption*						Non Adoption**		
	1a	1b	1c	1d	1e	1f	2a	2b	2c
Extraversion	●	●	●	●	●	○	●	●	○
Agreeableness	●	●	●	●	●	●		○	○
Responsibility	○	○		●	●	○	●	●	●
Neuroticism	○	○	○	○		○	○	○	○
Openness to Experience	●		●		●	○	○		●
Age		●	○	○	○	○	●	●	○
Consistency	0.81	0.80	0.81	0.80	0.80	0.80	0.70	0.70	0.70
Raw coverage	0.26	0.18	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.07	0.28	0.30	0.11
Unique coverage	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.08	0.11
Solution coverage	0.36						0.47		
Solution consistency	0.80						0,70		

Black circles represent the presence of a condition while voids circles indicate negation.